

Fundamental Study on Dimension Reduction of Covariance Matrix Modified by Data Assimilation

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the dimension reduction of a cross-section (XS) covariance matrix modified through data assimilation using criticality experiments. As low-rank approximation techniques, singular value decomposition (SVD) and pivoted Cholesky decomposition (PCD) were applied, and the data compression rate (DCR) and the reproducibility accuracy (RA) were evaluated for several cumulative contribution ratio (CCR) conditions in SVD. A simplified toy problem based on virtual criticality experiments was considered, where three nuclides (^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^1H) and three nuclear data (fission and (n, γ) XSs and $\bar{\nu}$ -value) were used. With reference to benchmark analysis reports for ICSBEP, ten virtual criticality experiments were prepared. Data assimilation based on the generalized linear least square (GLLS) method was applied to a JENDL-5-based covariance matrix in 252 energy groups, where the rank of covariance matrix was 1764. SVD achieved RA within 1% with a reduced rank of 422, where CCR was 0.999999, corresponding to DCR of 23.9%, which was slightly larger than the ratio of the number of components in prior and posterior covariance matrices. In contrast, PCD can reduce the rank more than SVD with DCR of 22.5%, which was approximately consistent with the case of prior covariance matrix. Consequently, under the present condition, PCD was found to be a more effective technique, enabling sufficiently dimension reduction of covariance matrix after data assimilation.

Keywords: dimension reduction, singular value decomposition, pivoted Cholesky decomposition, data assimilation, generalized linear least square method

1. INTRODUCTION

A safety analysis methodology for nuclear power plants has been developed to provide best-estimate predictions of core behavior and to quantify the range of possible variations in core safety parameters arising from uncertainties in input parameters, such as nuclear data and geometry [1]. A crucial aspect of this methodology is to identify and quantify uncertainties of diverse input parameters and their correlations.

In recent years, an application of data assimilation techniques, which incorporate the findings from criticality experiments to the uncertainty of nuclear data, has been discussed. By applying data assimilation techniques, the uncertainty prepared by evaluated nuclear data libraries originating from nuclear data measurement errors or theoretical modeling assumptions can be reduced.

Several studies have already demonstrated the application of data assimilation based on random sampling techniques for light water reactor (LWR) core analyses and can improve the accuracy of uncertainty quantification [2, 3]. However, once the data assimilation procedure is performed, the correlations of uncertainties, which do not originally exist, newly emerge across different nuclides and nuclear reactions. Namely, a dense and high-dimensional covariance matrices must be handled. Because such covariance matrices process an enormous volume of data, direct handling is impractical due to computational memory limitations.

This study investigates the applicability of dimension reduction techniques on covariance matrices after data assimilation and clarifies its data compression rate and reproduction accuracy. As a preliminary investigation, the present work approached a simplified toy problem considering data assimilation using virtual criticality experiments.

2. THEORETICAL DESCRIPTIONS

2.1 Nuclear Data Adjustment Method Using Sensitivity Coefficients

When sensitivity coefficients can be evaluated, data assimilation approach using these coefficients can be applied. According to [4], when experimental findings regarding neutronics parameter (\mathbf{R}) is given, both the posterior cross section (XSs, σ) and the posterior XS covariance matrix can be expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_{\sigma|\mathbf{R}} = \sigma_0 + \mathbf{K}_\sigma(\mathbf{R}_{\text{exp}} - \mathbf{R}_{\text{calc}}(\sigma_0)), \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{\sigma|\mathbf{R}} = \mathbf{M}_\sigma - \mathbf{K}_\sigma \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R},\sigma} \mathbf{M}_\sigma, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_\sigma = \mathbf{M}_\sigma \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R},\sigma}^T (\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R},\sigma} \mathbf{M}_\sigma \mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R},\sigma}^T + \mathbf{V}_e + \mathbf{V}_m)^{-1}, \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{\sigma|\mathbf{R}}$ is the posterior cross sections, σ_0 is the prior cross sections, \mathbf{R}_{exp} is the neutronics parameter obtained by experiments, and $\mathbf{R}_{\text{calc}}(\sigma_0)$ is that obtained by numerical simulations based on σ_0 , $\mathbf{M}_{\sigma|\mathbf{R}}$ and \mathbf{M}_σ represent the posterior and prior covariance matrix after and before data assimilation, respectively. $\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{R},\sigma}$ denotes the sensitivity coefficient of neutronics parameter (\mathbf{R}) on XS (σ). \mathbf{V}_e and \mathbf{V}_m are the experimental and modeling errors, respectively.

This study focused on the application of data assimilation to modified covariance matrix, thus only Equations (2) and (3) were used.

2.2 Low-Rank Approximation Techniques

In stochastic sampling-based uncertainty quantification in LWR core analysis, input parameters such as XSs were randomly perturbed using multivariate normal random number generated based on covariance matrix. Thus, this study used the singular value decomposition (SVD) and the pivoted Cholesky decomposition (PCD) to reduce the rank of covariance matrix after data assimilation from the standpoint of compatibility with random sampling. The following subsections give overview of these techniques.

2.2.1 SVD

SVD is one of the well-known approaches for low-rank approximation. By applying SVD, matrix \mathbf{A} can be decomposed as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} are orthogonal matrices containing the left and right singular vectors, respectively, and $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is a diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements represent the singular values of \mathbf{A} . When the matrix \mathbf{A} is a diagonal symmetric matrix such as the XS covariance matrix, \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} become the same.

When the rank of matrix \mathbf{A} is reduced from N to n ($n < N$), the number of singular values retained is determined by using the cumulative contribution ratio (CCR) of singular values, which is defined as follows:

$$\text{CCR} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n \Sigma_{ii}}{\sum_{i=0}^N \Sigma_{ii}}, \quad (5)$$

where Σ represents the diagonal element of the matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ (i.e., the singular value of matrix \mathbf{A}) in Equation (4). Once CCR reaches a predefined threshold, the data volume is reduced by setting the remaining diagonal elements to be zero.

After reducing the rank as described above, the matrix \mathbf{A} can be represented by using the matrices \mathbf{U}' , $\mathbf{\Sigma}'$, and \mathbf{V}' , which are approximated as reduced rank \mathbf{U} , $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, and \mathbf{V} , respectively, as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} \approx \mathbf{U}'\mathbf{\Sigma}'\mathbf{V}'^T, \quad (6)$$

2.2.2 PCD

PCD has been proposed as a low-rank approximation of a positive semi-definite matrix in recent years [5]. For the positive semi-definite matrix \mathbf{A} , the Cholesky decomposition (CD) represents it by using a lower triangular matrix \mathbf{L} as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}^T. \quad (7)$$

PCD is an extension of CD and can consider the low-rank approximation of matrix \mathbf{A} by using a reduced-rank matrix \mathbf{L}_m , which is approximated as reduced-rank \mathbf{L} in Equation (8), and a residual matrix \mathbf{E} as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{L}_m\mathbf{L}_m^T + \mathbf{E}. \quad (8)$$

However, Equation (8) has not reduced the total amount of data yet due to the existence of matrix \mathbf{E} . Thus, by only considering the diagonal elements of \mathbf{E} denoted as $\text{diag}(\mathbf{g})$, Equation (9) is rewritten as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} \approx \mathbf{L}_m\mathbf{L}_m^T + \text{diag}(\mathbf{g}). \quad (9)$$

PCD is employed in this study because it allows the construction of a matrix square root, making it directly applicable to the uncertainty evaluation based on the random sampling method, as follows:

$$\vec{r} \approx \mathbf{L}_m \vec{z}_1 + \text{diag}(\sqrt{\mathbf{g}}) \vec{z}_2. \quad (10)$$

In Equation (9), \vec{r} denotes the relative cross-section perturbation, while \vec{z}_1 and \vec{z}_2 are uniform random number vectors.

3. CALCULATION

3.1. Specification of Toy Problem

Energy groups and the findings of virtual criticality experiments, the posterior XS covariance matrix was evaluated based on Equations (2) and (3). The rank of this posterior XS covariance matrix was 1764, which corresponds that seven nuclides and reactions are considered in 252 energy groups.

To evaluate the compression efficiency and the reproduction accuracy achieved by SVD and PCD, a simplified toy problem was established. The toy problem assumed data assimilation using ten sets of virtual criticality experiments. A surrogate parameter representing an effective multiplication factor (k -effective) was modeled by considering XSs of ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^1H for fission and (n, γ) reactions and a ν -value (i.e., the number of neutrons emitted by fission reaction) as follows:

$$k = \frac{\sum_{g=1}^{NG} (\bar{\nu}_g^{U235} \sigma_{f,g}^{U235} N^{U235} \phi_g + \bar{\nu}_g^{U238} \sigma_{f,g}^{U238} N^{U238} \phi_g)}{\sum_{g=1}^{NG} (\sigma_{a,g}^{U235} N^{U235} \phi_g + \sigma_{a,g}^{U238} N^{U238} \phi_g + \sigma_{a,g}^{H1} N^{H1} \phi_g) + L}, \quad (11)$$

where k is the surrogate parameter considered as the k -effective. ν , σ_f , σ_a , ϕ_g , N , and NG are the $\bar{\nu}$ -value, the fission XS, the absorption XS given by the sum of fission and (n, γ) XSs, the neutron flux, the number density, and the number of energy groups, respectively. The subscript of g represents the energy group index. L is the adjustment parameter.

The fission and (n, γ) XSs and the $\bar{\nu}$ -value were generated by FRENDRY version 2 [6] in 252 energy groups [7] on the infinite dilution condition at 300 K based on JENDL-5 [8]. The neutron flux was evaluated by the method of characteristics-based neutron transport calculations by GENESIS [9] in two-dimensional pin-cell geometries assuming each referenced criticality experiment. The number density was treated as a spatially averaged value in the pin-cell geometries. L is the adjustment parameter and is evaluated so that k becomes the values predefined as corresponding to the calculation results of referenced criticality experiments [4]. These predefined values and the experiment and modeling errors used in Equation (10) were determined based on reference [4], which are summarized in Table I. The

covariance matrix for the fission and (n, γ) XSs and the ν -value was calculated by NJOY2016.78 [10]. Notably, the data assimilation in this study based on Equations (2) and (3) required the sensitivity coefficients, thus the sensitivity coefficients were calculated by directly applying a $\pm 5\%$ perturbation of $\bar{\nu}$, σ_f , or σ_a and evaluating the corresponding change in k .

Table I. General information of virtual criticality experiments.

ID	Predefined k [-]	Relative experimental error [%]	Relative modeling error [%]	Referenced Experiment in ICSBEP
1	0.99984	0.30	0.00	LCT-001-001
2	0.99741	0.20	0.23	LCT-002-001
3	1.00237	0.23	0.24	LCT-005-001
4	0.99815	0.20	0.19	LCT-005-014
5	0.99984	0.20	0.02	LCT-006-001
6	0.99687	0.14	0.31	LCT-007-001
7	1.00263	0.20	0.26	LCT-018-001
8	1.00221	0.34	0.22	LCT-026-001
9	1.00145	0.25	0.15	LCT-048-001
10	0.99892	0.16	0.10	LCT-079-001

3.2. Calculation Results

For the SVD-based approach, the singular values of the posterior XS covariance matrix are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Singular values of posterior XS covariance matrix.

Because the low-rank approximation based on SVD is generally performed based on CCR in Equation (5), this study preliminarily used CCR of 0.999, 0.9999, 0.99999, 0.999999, and 0.9999999, where the corresponding ranks were 255, 356, 396, 422, and 491.

To discuss the applicability of low-rank approximation techniques, the data compression rate (DCR) and the reproducibility accuracy (RA) were used. DCR represented the ratio of total amount of covariance matrix after reduced to rank n and that of original posterior covariance matrix and is defined as follows:

$$\text{DCR}_{\text{SVD}} = \frac{1764 \times n + n}{1764 \times 1764}. \quad (12)$$

On the other hand, when calculating the DCR for PCD, it is defined as follows:

$$DCR_{PCD} = \frac{1764 \times n + 1764}{1764 \times 1764} \quad (13)$$

Notably, the ratio of the total number of matrix components to be considered for the posterior and prior covariance matrices, as evaluated using Equation (13), based on the assumptions that σ_f , σ_a of U-235 and U-238 are correlated, no correlation is assumed for \bar{v} , and σ_a is considered for H-1, resulting in two 504×504 matrices and three 252×252 matrices, was approximately 22.4%:

$$DCR_{M_\sigma} = \frac{504 \times 504 \times 2 + 252 \times 252 \times 3}{1764 \times 1764}$$

The DCR corresponding to the above five cases of CCRs for both SVD and PCD is shown in Table II.

Table II. DCRs corresponding to CCRs of 0.999, 0.9999, 0.99999, 0.999999, and 0.9999999.

CCR[-]	DCR(SVD)[%]	DCR(PCD)[%]	Rank
0.999	14.5	14.5	255
0.9999	20.2	20.2	356
0.99999	22.4	22.4	395
0.999999	23.7	23.7	417
0.9999999	25.8	25.8	454

There was no significant variation in major parameters with respect to reduced rank between SVD and PCD. It was confirmed that when the CCR exceeds 0.99999, the data size becomes greater than that of the prior covariance matrix.

RA was defined as the ratio of standard deviations evaluated with the sensitivity coefficient and the posterior covariance matrix before and after low-rank approximation as follows:

$$RA_i = \frac{\sqrt{\tilde{S}_{R,\sigma,i} \mathbf{M}'_{\sigma|R} \tilde{S}_{R,\sigma}^T}}{\sqrt{\tilde{S}_{R,\sigma,i} \mathbf{M}_\sigma \tilde{S}_{R,\sigma}^T}} \quad (15)$$

where $\tilde{S}_{R,\sigma,i}$ is the vector of sensitivity coefficient in i -th virtual criticality experiment, $\mathbf{M}_{\sigma|R}$ and $\mathbf{M}'_{\sigma|R}$ are the posterior covariance matrix before and after low-rank approximation, respectively.

RA evaluated for five reduced-rank cases of CCRs in SVD is presented in Table III; the results for PCD are presented in Table IV. RA values greater than 0.990 are highlighted in bold and in red, based on the criterion that the uncertainty should be controlled within $\pm 1\%$, meaning that the original standard deviation can be reproduced with an accuracy better than 1% (i.e., within 0.990 to 1.010).

Table III. RA in five reduced-rank cases using SVD.

Rank	RA									
	ID1	ID2	ID3	ID4	ID5	ID6	ID7	ID8	ID9	ID10
255	0.856	0.859	0.835	0.822	0.838	0.835	0.861	0.839	0.904	0.833
356	0.951	0.958	0.950	0.935	0.935	0.947	0.961	0.948	0.956	0.942
395	0.989	0.989	0.988	0.987	0.989	0.990	0.992	0.991	0.994	0.990
417	0.999	1.000	0.999							
454	1.000									

Table IV. RA in five reduced-rank cases using PCD.

Rank	RA									
	ID1	ID2	ID3	ID4	ID5	ID6	ID7	ID8	ID9	ID10
255	0.990	0.845	0.999	0.990	1.000	0.922	1.001	1.000	0.992	0.994
356	0.999	0.952	0.999	0.999	1.000	0.998	0.994	1.000	0.994	0.997
395	1.000	0.989	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.999	1.000	1.000	0.998	0.999
417	1.000									
454	1.000									

In SVD, when the reduced rank was 417 or higher, the original standard deviation was reproduced within 1% error for all virtual criticality experiments, which can be considered as acceptable in practical use. DCR on CCR of 0.999999 was 23.7%. Therefore, when SVD was applied to reduce the rank of posterior covariance matrix, it was confirmed that total amount of data in covariance matrix to be handled was approximately 1.06 times larger than that in the prior covariance matrix.

For the while, in PCD, when the reduced rank was 396 or higher, the original standard deviation was reproduced within a 1% error for all virtual criticality experiments, which can be considered acceptable for practical use. The corresponding DCR was 22.4%. Therefore, when PCD was applied to reduce the rank of the posterior covariance matrix, it was confirmed that the total amount of data in the covariance matrix to be handled was approximately 1.004 times larger than that in the prior covariance matrix, indicating that the data size was compressed to a level nearly equivalent to that of the prior covariance matrix.

The results show that rank reduction of the posterior covariance matrix using PCD achieves reproducibility with less data than the SVD case. These findings suggest that, for the computational conditions considered here, PCD may be preferable to SVD as a dimensionality-reduction method.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, data assimilation based on GLLS method was performed for a XS covariance matrix. A low-rank approximation was applied to investigate the relationship between data size and reproducibility accuracy. The calculation conditions were defined for three nuclides (^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^1H) and three nuclear data (fission and (n, γ) XSs and $\bar{\nu}$ -value), and ten virtual criticality experiments were employed for data assimilation. Dimension reduction was conducted using SVD and PCD. Both DCR and RA were evaluated for several low-rank cases determined CCR in SVD to confirm the trade-off between the amount of retained data and RA.

For SVD, sufficient RA was obtained with DCR of 23.7%, which is slightly larger than the ratio of the number of components in prior and posterior covariance matrices. In contrast, PCD achieved comparable RA with DCR of 22.4%, which is approximately consistent with the case of prior covariance matrix.

Consequently, under the present conditions, PCD was found to be more effective, enabling sufficient dimension reduction of posterior covariance matrix after data assimilation. In future work, data assimilation and dimension reduction will be conducted under more realistic computational conditions by applying the proposed method to criticality experiment benchmarks in ICSBEP.

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